

Review

Advances in Regenerative Medicine and Tissue Engineering: Innovation and Transformation of Medicine

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Abstract: Regenerative medication (RM) is another approach to fix patients other than conventional medication and medical procedure. RM incorporates items from all the mainstays of medical care, for example drugs, biopharmaceuticals, clinical gadgets and cell treatments, to convey clinical results. All around the world, the cell treatment industry is simply developing, and keeping in mind that RM additionally draws upon non-cell-based medicines, undifferentiated organism based items and administrations have probably the most captivating chances and expectations with respect to beforehand serious sicknesses. In this exposition, the emphasis is on undeveloped cell based items and administrations. The fundamental examination question is the way scholastic exploration based advancements happen and can be moved to new organizations and treatments in the RM area. Hypothetically, this exposition expands on advancement frameworks, development related clinical innovation writing, and ability alliance hypothesis. Clinical innovation writing distinguishes parts of clinical innovation advancement development and how its components are conceptualized inside wellbeing advancement frameworks. Skill alliance hypothesis gives a decent clarification to how business develops and what skills are required. This thesis followed a valuable exploration approach and a solitary contextual analysis technique. The observational information comprises of 24 interviews and significant auxiliary information (reports, distributions, measurements, and so on) Utilizing observational information

and foundation writing, a development was created so as to clarify how development happens at the framework level and to distinguish the entertainers that are included.

Keywords: *Regenerative Medicine, Tissue Engineering*

Innovation in medical technology:

Wellbeing related advances cover a wide scope of advances beginning from science-based advances, for example, biotechnology and drugs, to designing based advances, for example, clinical gadgets (Meyer-Krahmer and Schmoch, 1998). As indicated by Blume (1992), expectedly the term 'clinical innovation' incorporates all things considered medications, gadgets and strategies, and this definition is applied in this thesis too. Djellal and Gallouj (2005) classified advancement in clinical innovation all the more significantly as biomedical or biopharmacological development, substantial development (mechanical frameworks including capital products, little things of gear, indicative or helpful hardware), and immaterial developments (care conventions, indicative or helpful systems, and so forth) Social advancements are additionally significant in wellbeing frameworks, and dissimilar to new items, social advancements don't have concentrated creation and far and wide appropriation however rather adaption to nearby conditions varying (Gardner et al., 2007). Concerning development in clinical innovation, various ventures have various sorts of advancement measures (Blume, 1992; Gelijns and Rosenberg, 1995). In biomedical ventures (additionally in RM cell treatments), much of the time development and at any rate item improvement follows a straight development measure whereby research produces thoughts that are tried with creatures and later in clinical trials⁵, lastly embraced to utilize (Gelijns and Rosenberg, 1994; Mason and Dunnill, 2008b). Be that as it may, especially with clinical gadgets, Gelijns and Rosenberg (1994) guarantee that a straight advancement process⁶ is just essential for reality and numerous developments depend on resulting adjustment of existing innovations for the necessities of the clinical area. The foundational idea of medical care is depicted in the HIS structure (Figure 1), which expands on the writing of advancement frameworks and clinical innovation, and which comprises of the segments of the framework and presents the elements of change as far as innovation advancement and its dispersion to clinical practice (Consoli and Ramlogan, 2008; Consoli and Mina, 2009). As HIS frameworks the fundamental parts in clinical innovation development measures, there are a few powers behind those empowering progression in clinical practice: propels in logical comprehension of a sickness; progresses in innovative abilities empowering the advancement of conclusion, treatments and

medicines; and learning in clinical practice empowering propels in clinical analysis and treatment (Nelson et al., 2011).

Figure 1. Health innovation system adapted from Consoli and Mina

Fig. 2 Regenerative medicine origins

Table 1 Applications of regenerative medicine therapies in different medical specialties

Medical Speciality	Pathology	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Clinical Trial Phase Pubmed Clinical Trial database	Patient numbers	Clinical Trial Study
Neurology	Parkinson's	Fetal porcine cells Transplantation of embryonic dopamine neurons	I, II	34	Fink 2001; Freed 2001
	Paraplegia, Spinal cord injuries	MSCs transplanted directly into injured spinal cord. Bone marrow nucleated cells injected intrathecally and intravenously coupled with MSC infusion by lumbar puncture	I, II	80	Park 2012; Jarocha 2015
	Multiple Sclerosis	IV infusion of MSCs Haemopoietic stem cell transplants	I, II	30	Connick 2012
Cardiology	Ischaemic cardiomyopathy, heart failure	Transendocardial injection of MSC derived from BM or adipose tissue Intracoronary injection of cardiac stem cells IV infusion of MSC	I, II	104	Heldman 2014; Hare 2014; Chugh 2012; Perin 2014
Respiratory	Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis	IV infusion of placental- derived MSC	I	8	Chambers 2014
	Chronic lung disease	IV infusion of HLA-matched allogeneic MSCs derived from BM/umbilical cord	I,II	62	Weiss 2013
Rheumatology	Osteoarthritis	Intra-articular injection of autologous or allogeneic MSC	I, II, III	104	Orozco 2013; Jo 2014
	Osteogenesis Imperfecta	Allogeneic bone marrow derived MSC Haemopoietic stem cell transplant plus MSC infusion	I	8	Horwitz 2002; Horwitz 2002
Orthopaedics	Fracture healing; Joint resurfacing; Osteoporosis	MSC combined with/without calcium sulphate Allogenic bone graft containing stem cells G-CSF-mobilised Haemopoietic stem cells with collagen scaffold for non-union fracture healing	I,II	96	Kuoroda 2014; Jones 2015; Bajada 2007
Haematology	Hematopoietic stem cell transplant (HSCT); Graft versus Host Disease (GvHD)	Prochymal (MSC) for severe refractory acute GvHD MSC infused with or following hematopoietic stem cell transplant	I, II, III	240	Prasad 2011; Ringden 2006; Perez-Simon 2011
Ophthalmology	Macular degeneration	ESC-derived retinal pigment epithelium	I	2	Schwartz 2012
Gastroenterology	Liver cirrhosis; Decompensated liver disease	MSC injected into peripheral or portal vein Autologous bone marrow mononuclear cells infused IV for liver cirrhosis UC-MS-C IV in fusion in decompensated liver disease	I,II	45	Kharaziha 2009; terai 2006; Zhang 2012
	Crohn's disease	Autologous hematopoietic stem cell transplantation for refractory Crohn's	I, II, III	98	Oyama 2005
Endocrinology	Diabetes (type I & 2)	Stem cell educator therapy with cord blood derived stem cells for insulin resistant type II diabetes Hematopoietic stem cell transplantation for new onset type I diabetes	I, II	65	Zhao 2013, D'Addio 2014
Nephrology/ Urology	Kidney transplant rejection	MSC based therapy to prevent rejection in living-related kidney transplants	I, II	159	Tan 2012

MSC mesenchymal stem cells, *BM* Bone marrow, *ESC* Embryonic Stem cells, *iPSC* induced Pluripotent stem cells, *IV* intravenous, *G-CSF* granulocyte-colony stimulating factor, *3D* 3-dimensional, *UC* umbilical cord

The era of regenerative medicine

The transition from TE into RegMed was justified by dramatic developments in the financial, scientific and political landscape. From a financial point of view, the first years of the 21st century, anticipated to bring the biotechnological revolution, were characterized by a disconnect between expectations and reality. As Lysaght noted in 2004 ‘...Although aggregate development costs exceed \$4.5 billion, the field has yet to produce a single profitable product’

On the scientific arena new technologies had come into play, with the very term TE being unable to accommodate them: The availability of human embryonic stem cells was bringing the cellular therapy at the front line of the field. Gene technology had come to a point, where a whole mammal could be cloned or genetically manipulated (the Monsanto swine case). Drug delivery systems and nanotechnology were developed and integrated in the design of biomaterials. The paramount significance of angiogenic processes for homeostasis, biointegration and upscaling of tissue engineered constructs became clear . Experimental activities were directed to encompass integrative strategies towards generation of autonomously vascularized bioartificial tissue elements. In addition tumour research was further advanced with the prospect of revolutionizing cancer treatment to round up progress in the biotechnological arena.

Regenerative medicine today

The recent financial meltdown knocked the air out of biotech by devastating its already floundering inflow of investment funds. From the end of 2007 until 2010 the industry had no initial public offering–introduction of shares in the public markets, and in the last 2 years we have witnessed a biotech asset yard sale with bigger pharma houses writing the cheque. The few survivors have turned their back to research altogether because like so often in science excellent scientific ideas and discoveries that provoke enthusiastic expectations turn out to be more difficult when it comes to routine clinical applications. When no immediate clinical results are visible industrial research funding becomes a problem. Investors are taking their money out of the industry thus driving stock price floors lower and by the end of 2009 as many as 79% of the biotech firms were trading under their opening price. No big hope for a cyclical recovery in funding exists momentarily because, as mentioned, investors have snubbed biotech for a decade. Even at the peak of the NASDAQ in October 2007 the percentage of industry players seeing their initial public enterprise value decline (trading under their opening price) was 59%. In the aggregate, even if the capital markets recover, it is unlikely that investors will flock to biotech hedge funds like it was believed earlier. Vivid fantasies of lifesaving new cures and tantalizing financial forecasts in the 1990s have made space for tight fists and raised eyebrows among investors.

However, this is hardly a phenomenon limited to the life sciences. Since 1995 the Gartner Advisory Group has devised a methodology to describe the ‘ups and downs’ of new technologies and relate them to business considerations.

These common general observations from the financial world seem to be also worthwhile to be considered by life science researchers, because of their analogy to scientific developments and their relevance to potential research funding sources. According to the hype cycles theory, a new technology is bound to undergo a series of five phases. As a first event there is a ‘technology trigger’. During this step, the new technology draws considerable attention by a breakthrough or a major press release. Soon thereafter, there is a ‘peak of inflated expectations’ during which over enthusiasm and overt publicity initiates a rage of investments. During this period there is a disconnection between expectations and performance. In the ‘trough of disillusionment’ failure to meet the expectations, renders the technology unfashionable and unattractive in the public mind and for investors. During the ‘slope of enlightenment’ although public interest has grossly deteriorated, in some centres the practical application and commercial potential is reassessed. Finally, in the ‘plateau of productivity’ the field re-emerges with viable concepts and profitability. The initial ideas are translated into business applications and products (Fig. 3).

Applications of tissue engineering and regenerative medicine strategies to bone repair

Bone defects and bone reconstruction are, probably, two of the most important issues in a TERM perspective, with several proposals advanced over the years [7,29,53,62,63]. Some injuries in anatomic areas such as distal tibia, talus or calcaneus, given their difficult irrigation and scarce soft tissue protection, usually are difficult to consolidate. This is a particularly critical problem in patients with a clinical history of multiple surgical interventions [33]. Bone grafts can cover the basic requirements for bone repair as they combine a scaffold, GFs and cells with osteogenic potential. Yet, the use of bone grafts is associated with several complications, i.e. non-unions [64],

incomplete filling of the defect and late graft fracture [63]. Furthermore, harvesting of autologous bone often results in donor site morbidity, which may vary with the location site and the applied technique [65]. Some technologies combining the use of GFs (namely BMPs) [7,28,29], cells [16] and/or scaffolds [66,67], adapted or not to a surgical intervention have achieved promising results in cases where several previous surgeries have failed systematically [3,33,68]. BMPs, specifically BMP-2, BMP-4 and BMP-7, have been known for over a decade for inducing osteogenic cell differentiation in vitro and in vivo [68]. The value of recombinant human BMP-2 (rhBMP-2) has been evaluated in a prospective study for treating open tibial shaft fractures [69]. A significant reduction of a secondary intervention was observed in the rhBMP-2 group as compared with the standard care group, suggesting that the use of GFs could accelerate healing of fractures and soft tissue, reduce hardware failure, and thus re-operation owing to delayed healing/non-union. Still, there are only few available GFs for clinical use in bone regeneration besides BMP-2, BMP-7 and growth and differentiation factor-5 (GDF-5) [70]. Recently, Kleinschmidt et al. [70] reported that the use of a mutant GDF-5 (obtained by introducing BMP-2 residues into GDF-5) demonstrated enhanced osteogenesis and long bone formation capacity [70]. When the use of GFs alone is not recommended, as in the treatment of large bone defects, stem cells and scaffolds are a very promising alternative to standard procedure. Stem cell-based TERM strategies require three main steps: (i) cells are harvested, isolated and expanded, (ii) scaffolds are seeded with the induced cells, and (iii) cell-seeded scaffolds are re-implanted in vivo [68]. The aim of TERM is the substitution of the missing tissue with the ex vivo tissue-engineered construct. There are several reports [71,72] on the application of different scaffolds combined with stem cells (mostly MSCs derived from bone marrow or adipose tissue). These have shown favourable autogenous bone grafting and no donor site morbidity [68]. Scaffold choice is still under investigation in order to be standardized. Biodegradable synthetic polyesters [73], calcium phosphate ceramics [74,75] and chitosan–alginate [76] are some of the scaffolds that have proved to have significant value in the treatment of bone defects. Cancedda et al. [63] have provided relevant information and new insights on the importance of scaffold architecture towards enhancing de novo bone formation within scaffolds in vivo.

Applications of biomaterials

Hyaline cartilage serves as a low-friction surface with high wear resistance for weight-bearing joints. Unfortunately, it possesses an avascular and alymphatic profile which limits its autonomous regenerative capacity. The application of differentiated cells in the clinic presents additional problems such as cells' tendency towards losing their differentiated phenotype in a two-dimensional culture (e.g. chondrocytes) and to differentiate towards a broblast-like phenotype [114]. To overcome this problem in the treatment of cartilage lesions, different scaffolds have been developed for supporting cell adhesion, proliferation and maintenance of phenotype in an effective manner [4,115]. Among the several scaffolds proposed in an attempt to better fulfil the requirements of cartilage regeneration process, there are substantial differences regarding the materials chosen and their physical forms (i.e. fibers, meshes and gels). Solid scaffolds provide a substrate on which cells can adhere, whereas gel scaffolds physically entrap the cells [116]. The biomaterials used can be classified as synthetic or natural. Synthetic matrices present mechanical properties and degradation rates more easily tuned as compared with that of natural polymers, but some biocompatibility concerns might be raised owing to their degradation products and potential effect on native tissue and implanted cells. However, innovations in chemistry and materials science have been improving their biocompatibility [116]. Among the natural and synthetic materials that have been investigated (e.g. gellan gum, alginate, silk fibroin, chitosan, hydroxyapatite, collagen, hyaluronic acid (HA), polyglycolic acid and polylactic acid) [117], few have been used in ankle lesions, probably due to the lack of studies in the field of ankle tissue regeneration.

Use of Nanoparticles

In vivo maturation of engineered tissues requires a well synchronized series of events involving host immune system, circulatory system and cellular component of the implanted material. Physicochemical properties of the scaffolds and the presence/immobilization of bioactive agents within the scaffolds can help in achieving a precise control over maturation. Herein, we reviewed the use of nanoscale structures with different material properties for enhancing the properties of tissue engineering scaffolds by rendering them antimicrobial, providing sequential release of several growth factors, by concentrating necessary contrasting agents for monitoring, by improving mechanical properties of bioprinted structures as bioink supplements and also by providing structural elements such a HAp in nanoscale to induce tissue specific reactions. The future tissue engineering solutions might contain multiple components for all these aspects to have

higher control over integration, monitoring and long-term safety of engineered tissues. Focus of nanoscale delivery systems should not only be on manufacturing advanced delivery systems but also on also on evaluating systemic cytotoxic effect and immune responses of these systems. Such studies could provide better understanding of biocompatibility of vast numbers of nanoscale delivery systems and will direct the future studies with higher success rate in cost-effective approach. For this aim, the different nanoparticle types of different materials (metals, ceramics, magnetic/paramagnetic materials and polymers) provide a strong toolbox for tissue engineered artificial organ functionalization.

In summary, stem cell research based on nanotechnology has obtained a lot of achievement in the field of regenerative medicine of orthopedic surgery, showing good prospects in clinical applications. But nanotechnology applied to stem cell research is still in its early stages, and there are a number of key issues to be solved. The objective of tissue engineering research with stem cell is to develop a system to accurately simulate the in vivo microenvironment system in vitro; however, the mechanism is not very clear regarding how nanomaterials similar to extracellular matrix in morphology affect the function of stem cells.

Biomaterials and their scaffold used for tissue engineering in orthopedic surgery can be manufactured by nanohydroxyapatite, titanium, calcium phosphate, graphene oxide, carbon nanotubes, or the compound of them. These composite scaffolds have both nanomaterials properties and good biocompatibility and low toxicity which render it a very broad application prospect in orthopedic surgery regenerative medicine by some nanoscale surface topography or molecular biology mechanism, including the regulation of stem cell biological behavior (such as attachment, proliferation, and differentiation), the improvement of bone tissue regeneration promising skeletal defects repair, internal fixation surgery, and spinal fusion in orthopedic surgery, the potential application in cartilage tissue engineering and recovery at tendon-to-bone insertion site, and the nerve tissue engineering for spinal cord injury.

Although the research of stem cell nanotechnology is facing many difficulties in regenerative medicine of orthopedic surgery, its potential applications have caused great concern. With the development of nanotechnology and stem cell research, the investigation of stem cell based on nanotechnology will be studied more in depth and will provide new methods for stem cell therapy and tissue engineering in regenerative medicine of orthopedic surgery.

Last contemplations

The suitable treatment for OCD fix is as yet disputable. The ideal strategy would recover a tissue with biomechanical properties like typical hyaline articular ligament, with decreased dismalness and expenses. The magnificent toughness of results got by ACI or MACI over the long haul is entrenched what's more, stands out forcefully from the drawn out outcomes revealed for bone-marrow-invigorating methods, (for example, scraped area, penetrating or on the other hand microfractures). An assortment of biomaterials including polymers and earthenware production have been proposed for recovery of the ligament of OCDs, also, composite frameworks (for example polymers joined with earthenware production), particularly whenever cultivated with autologous cells and additionally GFs, appear to improve biomechanical results. Up to now a couple of clinical preliminaries on lower leg recuperating have been portrayed, while a platform way to deal with the treatment of knee chondral sores has been generally utilized in clinical practice, with astounding or great clinical outcomes generally reported in the writing. New methodologies must be considered to bone osteocondral absconds so as to improve reclamation. Despite the fact that there are particularities of such territory, different biomaterials with critical brings about knee OCDs might be applied to the lower leg injuries. TERM approaches are changing the standards of medication also, careful practice. Notwithstanding, the achievement of these innovations as of now and in future requests profound information on local tissue science and comprehension of its fix components and reaction to injury, just as the new biomaterials viable. Fundamental standards of science and other 'essential sciences' (understanding essential just as principal, never as basic) must be notable by all specialists since just in this way will they have the option to comprehend, adjust and aid the improvement of this information to clinical practice. TERM approaches have demonstrated viability in clinical cases what's more, issues which utilized determination rules not beforehand understood by 'ordinary' helpful fix and additionally substitution choices. Nonetheless, indiscriminating utilization of any encouraging method is one of the best approaches to debilitate or even square its legitimate turn of events.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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